

SafeSCHEMA: Multi-domain Orchestration of Slices based on SafeRL for B5G Networks

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Abstract—The success of Software-Defined Networking and Network Function Virtualization enabled providers to partially automate the decision-making of various network operating workflows. Network slicing is an innate feature of the Fifth Generation (5G) and Beyond-5G (B5G) networks, bringing many advantages but also increasing the complexity of managing such networks. In this context, automation tools based on Artificial Intelligence (AI) have become a preeminent instrument of automation used by the industry, as it would be impossible to manually provision and manage such a vast and dynamic infrastructure. Safe interaction of the AI agents with the network is one of the predominant challenges, especially when Reinforcement Learning (RL) is used in critical environments. This is particularly important when the RL agent actions have a high or irreversible impact on the network or service. Slice management is one of the major features that operators want to automate, to offer future services at large scales with manageable complexity to the operator. However, during the exploration phase, RL agents can cause significant performance degradation during operation and possibly introduce irreversible damage to the service being offered. To address this major challenge, we propose a multi-agent, modular, SafeRL architecture for distributed slice orchestration. We study the problem of zero-touch slice management and orchestration, in the context of Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communication services for B5G networks. Our results demonstrate improved performance over competing solutions, while ensuring the safety of the performed actions during real-time slice orchestration.

Index Terms—Slicing, Distributed Reinforcement Learning, Safe Reinforcement Learning, Service Function Chain.

I. INTRODUCTION

The unprecedented scale and dynamicity of the Fifth Generation (5G) and Beyond-5G (B5G) networks drives the operators towards automated and autonomous management systems that operate with minimal human intervention. Intelligent, AI-powered solutions are an integral part of these solutions. Moreover, there is a stringent need for zero-touch network orchestration solution that is reliable and safe to operate with little to no human intervention in a fully functional telecommunications network.

The adoption of Software-Defined Networking (SDN) and Network Function Virtualization (NFV) into the telecommunications networks enabled a more flexible way to deliver scalable services with many different end-user requirements, in a cost efficient manner. Network Slicing is a major key enabler; however, network slicing also introduces additional

complexity in terms of the provisioning and management of these slices, which, coupled with the scale of these networks, require automated orchestration solutions.

Machine Learning (ML) has been a research area for a prolonged time, and in the past couple of decades, it was adopted into many sectors where it proved to bring a new set of solutions to many sectors in the area of automation. With ML, human-level cognition can be used to automate management workflows in an economical and scalable way, as there is no human intervention in the process.

In telecom systems, ML has been initially adopted for reactive management, however with the added complexity in 5G and B5G systems, there is an active movement towards using ML for more proactive management. Still, there are hurdles to overcome before ML can become a reliable solution in network management automation. It is well known that ML-driven algorithms are not able yet to provide human-level decision-making beyond some basic scenarios. Issues such as instability that emerges from their actions might trouble the network workflows, causing expensive or irreversible damage. On the other hand, it is expensive and not scalable to handle network management by human operators. A middle-ground solution must be conceived to allow the adoption of ML in the telecommunications networks to enable automatic network optimizations and Service-Level Agreement (SLA) maintenance.

In this paper, we propose a modular architecture capable of safe and automated slice management for networks that consist of multiple interconnected domains that span multiple locations. The architecture consists of multiple distributed agents that co-operate to orchestrate the slice elements, specifically to manage the placement of the Virtual Network Functions (VNFs). RL-enabled agents are wrapped with a Safety Shield, which prevents the execution of unsafe placement actions that can be proven dangerous for the operation of the End-to-End (E2E) slice performance. Our contribution is threefold by:

- Introducing a modular and flexible architecture that can be deployed in multi-domain networks with multiple slices and services;
- Providing a solution to minimize the unsafe actions of the RL-agents, while still allowing enough autonomy to explore the space;
- Demonstrating a collaborative agent Key Performance Indicator (KPI) optimization. Specifically, latency mini-

mization for Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communication (URLLC) services will be used as our use-case scenario.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II provides a discussion of related work, Section III an overview of the System Model architecture, while introducing the formulation of all network components. Section IV introduces an in-depth analysis of the problem statement and the proposed solution theoretical background. Section V showcases the simulation setup and evaluates the performance compared to other solutions from the literature. Finally, Section VI presents brief conclusion and our future directions.

II. RELATED WORK

Since autonomous slice resource management and orchestration is a crucial aspect of 5G / B5G networks, topics such as VNF placement, Service Function Chain (SFC) embedding and orchestration have recently been studied in conjunction with the use of RL.

For instance, in [1] Tran et al. use Deep RL to automate the placement of VNF-Forwarding Graphs (VNF-FG) considering the constraints of the underlying infrastructure. On the other hand, Ye et al. in [2] conceive a heuristic algorithm that optimizes network bandwidth consumption by taking advantage of the VNF placement.

Despite the advancements, single-agent algorithms are unable to provide efficient solutions for large-scale networks with huge problem and actions spaces due to their centralized design. Only a few works have tackled the multi-domain VNF embedding issue. Authors in [3] formulate the multi-domain VNF-FG embedding as an Integer Linear Programming problem and introduce a decentralized network utilization optimization by proposing several multi-node algorithms.

There is an apparent need for Safe Reinforcement Learning (SafeRL) decision-making when automating network procedures. Consequently, several methods have been proposed to achieve safety in the context of SafeRL. In [4], Elsayed-Aly introduces the concept of shielding in which a temporal logic is proposed to filter out unsafe actions proposed by the RL agent. Similar works on safe strategies include the use of accumulated past knowledge [5], making conservative action choices that prioritize avoiding the worst-case scenario. Other works, such as [6], [7], request guidance from a human operator or an external agent when the operating state is considered risky.

The work in this paper is based on the success of our previous work [8] and [9], where the SafeRL architecture was applied for Radio Access Network optimization. In this work, the SafeRL architecture is used to optimize and secure the multi-slice, multi-domain, zero-touch management and orchestration in conjunction with the SCHEMA architecture in [10].

III. SYSTEM MODEL & ARCHITECTURE

For illustrative purposes, Fig. 1 shows a network composed of multiple cloud domains ($1 \dots n$), that are distributed over a wide area. The network is modeled so that domains located

at the edge of the network provide lower latency access to services for the end-users u . The slices s are defined as network slices that are composed of multiple chained VNFs.

Figure 1. Network graph model.

The parameters u, v represent two nodes, and uv is the physical link that connects nodes u and v . To accommodate the functions of an NFV-enabled network, the nodes have two types, one for network switching and one as an NFV-enabled computing node.

Network resources are finite and represented as follows:

- C_{uv}^{bw} represents the capacity of the network link uv .
- C_u^{cpu} the number of available CPU cores of the computing node u .
- C_u^{ram} the amount of available memory of the computing node u .
- C_u^{hdd} the available storage space of node u .

A. Network Slices, Deployment & Orchestration

Slices s are represented as graphs $G_s = (\mathcal{V}_s, \mathcal{E}_s, \mathcal{U}_s)$ in which the flow of data between the VNFs has a predefined order. The notation \mathcal{V}_s denotes the *source*, the *destination* and *intermediate* nodes that the slice s traverses. The data flow of the chained VNFs of slice s is represented as a list $u_{source} \rightarrow u_1 \dots u_j \rightarrow u_{destination}$. The traffic traverses through the intermediate nodes $u_1 \dots u_j$ using the *Dijkstra* algorithm. Variables u_s, v_s represent two nodes in G_s , while \mathcal{E}_s represents the links $u_s v_s$ that connect neighboring VNFs, served by the nodes u_s and v_s in G_s . Finally, \mathcal{U}_s defines the set of users that utilize the slice s .

Fully deployed and operating slices s have a particular way of traversing the network, which cannot be split or reversed. Traffic is flowing from i_{first} to i_{last} by traversing all intermediate nodes $i_1 \dots i_j$ as described in the following equation:

$$\sum_{u \in \mathcal{V}} \sum_{u_s v_s \in \mathcal{E}_s} (z_{uv}^{u_s v_s} - z_{vu}^{u_s v_s}) = \begin{cases} -1, u \text{ is the Source} \\ 1, u \text{ is the Destination} \\ 0, u \text{ is an Intermediate} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $z_{uv}^{u_s v_s}$ and $z_{vu}^{u_s v_s}$ are either 0 or 1 indicating whether $u_s v_s$ traverses the link uv and computing node u respectively.

If a physical link uv is used by the slice s , then the nodes connected u and v must be traversed too as follows:

$$z_u^{u_s v_s} z_v^{u_s v_s} = \begin{cases} 1, z_{uv}^{u_s v_s} = 1 \\ 0, \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

B. Network Constraints & SLA Violations

Slices s are categorized into three distinct classes:

- \mathcal{S} describe the instantiated slices.
- \mathcal{T} the terminated slices.
- \mathcal{R} the redirected slices.

Redirected slices occur when the VNF placement violates the service SLA for this slice, defined as ϕ_s^{delay} , or when there are inadequate resources in the nodes to host the service VNFs.

At any time interval the total allocation of bandwidth and computational resource consumption cannot exceed the available resources in links $\forall uv$, nodes $\forall u$ and VNFs $\forall m$ as described in the following constraints:

$$\sum_{u_s v_s \in \mathcal{E}_s} \sum_{s \in \mathcal{SUTUR}} \phi_s^{bw} z_{uv}^{u_s v_s} \leq \omega_{uv}^{bw} C_{uv}^{bw}, \quad (3)$$

$$\sum_{u_s v_s \in \mathcal{E}_s} \sum_{s \in \mathcal{SUTUR}} \phi_s^{cpu} p_u^m \leq C_u^{cpu}, \quad (4)$$

$$\sum_{u_s v_s \in \mathcal{E}_s} \sum_{s \in \mathcal{SUTUR}} \phi_s^{ram} z_u^{u_s v_s} \leq \omega_u^{ram} C_u^{ram}, \quad (5)$$

$$\sum_{u_s v_s \in \mathcal{E}_s} \sum_{s \in \mathcal{SUTUR}} \phi_s^{hdd} z_u^{u_s v_s} \leq \omega_u^{hdd} C_u^{hdd}, \quad (6)$$

where the variable p_u^m is 1 if VNF m is placed in node u . The variables $z_{uv}^{u_s v_s}$ and $z_u^{u_s v_s}$ have binary values, as denoted in the previous section, to indicate whether $u_s v_s \in \mathcal{E}_s$ traverses the link uv and node u respectively. The variable ϕ_s^{bw} represents the bandwidth consumption of the physical links due to the activation of slice s on these links. $\phi_{s,m}^{cpu}$, $\phi_{s,m}^{ram}$ and $\phi_{s,m}^{hdd}$ are used for the computational resources that the slice s VNFs occupy. Finally, ϕ_s^{delay} indicates the maximum tolerated delay by the predefined SLA, the maximum slice latency in our case.

C. Delay Model & Maximum Tolerated Delay

We denote latency in links and other elements as follows: d_{uv} the delay of link uv , d_u the delay caused by the computing node hardware and d_m the delay caused by the VNF overlay. Instantiated and running slices s in the network show an E2E delay to the slice users $u \in \mathcal{U}_s$, which is highly dependent on the VNF placement and the number of hops. This delay can be expressed as the sum of all delays and cannot exceed its slice SLA delay ϕ_s^{delay} as indicated:

$$\sum_{uv \in \mathcal{E}} \sum_{u_s v_s \in \mathcal{E}_s} d_{uv} z_{uv}^{u_s v_s} + \sum_{u \in \mathcal{V}} \sum_{u_s v_s \in \mathcal{E}_s} d_u z_u^{u_s v_s} + \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \sum_{u_s \in \mathcal{V}_s} d_m z_m^{u_s} \leq \phi_s^{delay} \quad (7)$$

The inability to achieve the inequality of the equation moves the slice $s \in \mathcal{S}$ from operating to redirected $s \in \mathcal{R}$ before the end of the current iteration. It triggers a cost penalty used in the reward function to adjust the future actions of the local RL agents, as discussed in the next section.

The E2E slice delay D_s during the current interval can be calculated as follows:

$$D_s = \sum_{uv \in \mathcal{E}} \sum_{u_s v_s \in \mathcal{E}_s} d_{uv} z_{uv}^{u_s v_s} + \sum_{u \in \mathcal{V}} \sum_{u_s v_s \in \mathcal{E}_s} d_u z_u^{u_s v_s} + \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \sum_{u_s \in \mathcal{V}_s} d_m z_m^{u_s}, \quad (8)$$

$$\mathbb{D} = \sum_{s \in \mathcal{SUTUR}} D_s. \quad (9)$$

where D_s is the sum of all slice links, computing nodes hardware and VNFs overlay delays that are traversed by the chain. The total slice delay \mathbb{D} of the current iteration can be expressed as the E2E slice delay D_s of all slices.

IV. SAFE DISTRIBUTED REINFORCEMENT LEARNING

In this work, we deploy SafeRL agents per each domain to orchestrate the slice VNFs inside the borders of a domain n . Additionally, a module called the *Auction Mechanism* that enables for inter-domain migration is developed. During the operation, the *Auction Mechanism* circulates through the slice VNFs and the domain SafeRL agents bid to win the auction and receive the VNF in auction. The goal is to use multiple distributed SafeRL agents one per domain to orchestrate slice VNFs with respect to a specific KPI, e.g., E2E average slice latency in this work, in a scalable way.

A. Intra-Domain Distributed Orchestration

The domains are responsible to orchestrate the hosted VNFs locally and asynchronously, to avoid unnecessary migrations. The local agents consist of multiple modules that cooperate to perform the task of safe inter-domain, intra-slice VNF placement. Our approach is a SafeRL-enabled agent based on the work of Aumayr et al. [9] that uses a modular shield architecture and a safe baseline. The action proposed by the RL agent is benchmarked against a safe baseline through a *Safety Shield* that chooses the safest action to be performed on the environment.

Figure 2. SafeRL-based local domain architecture.

Briefly, the Local Agent architecture and components, as shown in Fig. 2, are the following:

1) *Environment*: This component represents the environment that the agent is interacting with, modeled as a standard RL problem. It provides interaction with the local domain n part of the network infrastructure which was described in the previous section.

2) *RL Agent*: The *RL agent* is continuously trained during the interaction with the *Environment* to improve their future recommended actions for VNF placement. The agent indirectly interacts with the *Environment* by proposing actions to the *Safety Shield* and getting feedback on the actual action performed.

3) *Safe Baseline*: The *Safe Baseline* provides a default action, usually sub-optimal in terms of performance, yet safe with regards to what safety indicates for the system at hand. In our scenario, we define safety as an action that does not lead to breaking any service SLAs. *Safe Baseline* is a rule-based algorithm that recommends actions satisfying safety rules, usually designed by domain experts. Baselines also receive the current state of the *Environment* as feedback, to suggest future actions.

4) *Safety Shield*: This component is the middleman between the *RL agent* and the *Environment*. In the non-Safe RL architecture, the RL agent directly interacts with the environment and receives feedback. On the contrary, in the SafeRL architecture the *Safety Shield* is a broker between the *RL Agent* and the *Environment* to protect the environment from unsafe actions. The *Safety Shield* collects the actions proposed by the *RL agent* and the *Baseline* and selects a final safe action to be performed in the *Environment*. The environment feedback includes the action that is actually performed by the shield on the environment and is fed back to *RL agent* and the *Baseline*, so that they are aware of the new state of the *Environment* before the next iteration.

5) *Safety Logic*: The logic provides constraints to the *Safety Shield*. It includes the logic used to determine what is the safest action between the one proposed by *RL agent* and the *Safe Baseline* at any time. Due to the modularity of this architecture, it supports various implementations.

We model the intra-domain VNF placement and orchestration problem as a Markov Decision Process (MDP) which consists of a *State*, an *Action Space* and a *Reward Function*.

The MDP problem space can be defined as follows:

- *State Space* Consists of the intra-domain computational resources of the domain nodes u_n . The local domain state space S_n is defined as a set that contains the VNF hosting computing requirements, the slice SLA and the domain computing and networking utilization ratio for each network element:

$$S_n = (w_{uv}^{bw}, w_u^{cpu}, w_u^{ram}, w_u^{hdd}, \dots, \phi_s^{delay}, \phi_s^{bw}, \phi_{s,m}^{cpu}, \phi_{s,m}^{ram}, \phi_{s,m}^{hdd})^T, \quad (10)$$

- *Action Space* The *Confidence Vector* A_n , a vector that contains an offer $\in [-1, 1]$ for each domain server u_n to receive the VNF currently to be placed. The maximum of this local action indicates an intra-domain VNF migration:

$$A_n = (i_0, \dots, i_{u_n})^T, \quad (11)$$

- *Reward* Consists of cost function expressed in (12). The objective of all domains n is to maximize the sum of the function R^{shared} in every iteration and thus, converging

in a common state-action that enables cooperation among the domains:

$$R^{shared} = \frac{1}{w_D * \mathbb{D}} + P, \quad (12)$$

where w_D is the weight of the total slice delay \mathbb{D} .

In addition, we define a penalty function that is applied when the SLA described in (7) of the slice s is violated:

$$P = -w_P(D_s > \phi_s^{delay}), \quad (13)$$

where w_P expresses the penalty weight.

B. Inter-Domain VNF Orchestration Auction Mechanism

The *Auction Mechanism* is a system that enables inter-domain VNF migration. It acts as an auctioneer between the domains who bid with their actions to receive a slice VNF to their domain.

Figure 3. Overview of the multi-domain and distributed Auction Mechanism. All local domains can orchestrate VNFs in parallel and exchange VNFs only during an auction.

The *Auction Mechanism* repeats the following steps in every iteration:

1) *Selection*: The *Auction Mechanism* circulates through the slice VNFs during an *interval*, a predefined time frame. As an auctioneer, it selects the next VNF in round robin fashion for the auction process.

2) *Participation*: The per domain n Local Agents act as bidders that generate their bid, an action A_n produced by the *Local RL Agent* and secured by the *Safety Shield* as previously described.

3) *Auction*: The mechanism receives all domain bids and selects the highest bidder (the domain with the highest bid). The candidate domain is notified to initiate the migration.

4) *Orchestration*: If the candidate domain is not the current domain, the inter-domain migration is initiated. Otherwise, the domain agent performs an intra-domain migration based on the safeRL action to the node with the highest bid.

The *Auction Mechanism* is only responsible for the inter-domain communication. It is non-essential for the local domain orchestration. The *Auction Mechanism* can be deployed quickly as a stateless container at any node of the network, eliminating the single point of failure.

V. SIMULATION RESULTS & EVALUATION

A custom-made OpenAI Gym environment [11] has been developed using *Python* to simulate the SDN-NFV network. The simulator is based on Containernet [12], an advanced fork of Mininet [13] network emulator, which was used for evaluation by many works in the related literature (e.g., [14] and [15]). It simulates a realistic virtual network, Virtual Machine hosting, switching, and application code for developing and experimenting with SDN-NFV networks. The examined network topology is a variation of the *2005 Nordu European network*, from *The Internet Topology Zoo* dataset [16], adjusted to fit the requirements of the study. The RL agents were developed using *TensorFlow* [17] and the high-level *Keras API* open-source library [18].

A. SafeSCHEMA Configuration & Baselines

As *Safe Baseline* we use an algorithm called *Compu* that migrates the VNF to the local server with the most resources available as a default action. This action is deemed safe, as the inter-domain servers are located in close proximity and introduce less latency than servers located in different domains, leaving computational resources as the major source of additional delay. Overloaded servers introduce software delays, thus resource utilization should be a decisive factor and be prioritized compared to the server distance when it comes to designing a baseline action which is applied in case of an unsafe action proposed by the *RL Agent*. We use it as a demonstration of custom rules.

The performance of SafeSCHEMA is compared with three main baselines:

- 1) *SCHEMA*: is a non-safeRL version of SafeSCHEMA. Comparing it with a flat distributed solution.
- 2) *DQN*: is a DRL-based orchestration algorithm located in a central location. It is a common type of baseline approach in the related research literature, such as in [19], [1], and [2].
- 3) *Static*: is a placement method adopted by many works as the default baseline [20].

B. Performance Evaluation

In Fig. 4a, we depict the average E2E slice latency in milliseconds (ms) for a varying number of users. We observe that the average slice latency increases with the number of users as they occupy more network resources and limit the possible VNF placement options that satisfy all users with low latency, no matter of their location in the network. It is apparent that the guaranteed SLA, defined as 10ms for the slice is respected by SafeSCHEMA. Additionally, it is able to outperform the distributed baseline of SCHEMA as it filters any unwanted proposed actions from the agents that will violate the SLA, thus lowering the average slice latency.

Fig. 4b demonstrates the scalability of SCHEMA and the superiority of SafeSCHEMA as the *Safety Shield* module and the *Baseline* protect the network from unsafe RL agent actions. Introducing more domains in the network exponentially increases the complexity of the orchestration, but as we can see in Fig. 4b SCHEMA and SafeSCHEMA were

Figure 4. (a) Average slice latency per number user. (b) Average slice latency per number of domains. Lower is better for both figures.

able to resist the degradation of the performance as the state space grew with the introduction of new domains. This behavior can be attributed to the distributed architecture that orchestrates the slice VNFs locally and exchanges them only when needed by both algorithms. The performance superiority of SafeSCHEMA can be attributed to the use of the *Safety Shield* that prevents any unsafe actions from being executed in the network and replaces them with non-optimal but safe actions that can keep the average slice latency low.

Figure 5. (a) Average slice latency per number of slices. (b) Average slice latency per number of chained slice VNFs. Lower is better for both figures.

Fig. 5a presents the performance of the compared algorithms during the operation of multiple slices, hence their ability to maintain performance, demonstrating the ability to scale horizontally. We observe again that both distributed solutions were able to outperform the rest of the baselines. SafeSCHEMA takes the edge in this scenario by having a 15.38% lower latency than SCHEMA. The reason for this is the *divide et impera* approach that drastically reduces the orchestration complexity and tackles it with minimal overhead.

In Fig. 5b the average slice latency is plotted against the

number of chained VNFs on each of 4 slices. It is clear, especially in the case of 2 and 4 chained slice VNFs that SafeSCHEMA was able to maintain a lower slice latency by 20.18% from SCHEMA and 126.62% from Static in the case of 8 VNFs.

Figure 6. (a) Latency deviation per algorithm. (b) VNF Occupancy index represents the average number of hosted VNFs per total number of VNFs for 100 iterations of simulated traffic.

Finally, in Fig. 6a we show the latency deviation of all competing solutions of our work in the original *2005 Nordu European network* topology [16] for 4 slices. It is apparent that from the two distributed solutions, only SafeSCHEMA was able to avoid violating the slice SLA of 10ms as the *Safety Shield* protects the network from unsafe actions. Fig. 6b presents the behavior of SafeSCHEMA that gravitated towards consolidating the chained slice VNFs to reduce the number of hops to the end-user and thus, reduce the average slice latency.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we propose a multi-agent, modular SafeRL architecture for distributed slice orchestration. As a concrete use case for our proposed architecture, we study the latency reduction for a URLLC service in 5G/B5G networks, which is evaluated using a simulated environment that is configured to recreate a real-world network. We have proposed SafeSCHEMA, an innovative, multi-agent and distributed RL-based service orchestration framework, coupled with an *Auction Mechanism* that the local domains use to exchange VNFs between the domains. The distributed agents discover how to cooperate through a common reward function and perform VNF placements in multiple domains through an auction. The results show that, compared to our proposed solution, unrestricted RL agents explore unsafe regions of the state-action space during exploration, leading to the SLAs being broken. In contrast, SafeSCHEMA leads to better performance and scalability. Our future work includes experimenting with other options for the *Safety Logic*, including taking input from an Analytic Engine that provides slice latency predictions.

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